

Primordial Sound of Music

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Abstract

Sound is a type of Energy made up of vibrations. According to Scientists Big Bang Theory, it suggests that the Universe was created as a result of an extremely large explosion. (Sound) This is the First Primordial Sound. In Music one of the Varieties of Nada is Anagatha Nada which is the Primordial Sound. Yogis created this Sound through Kundalini. Ohm is also considered to be the Primordial Sound of the Universe. It is the original Vibration of Universe. From this all the other Vibrations are able to manifest. This is praised by all most all the Composers like Tyagaraja, Dikshita, Syama Sastri and soon.

Keywords: Big Bang Theory- Aagatha , Anagatha Nada- Yogi- Galaxy – Cosmic Energy – Omkara – Pranava – Bija Mantra – Frequency – Tyagaraja- Dikshita – Syama Sastri

INTRODUCTION

Indian Classical Music is one of the leading systems of music in the world with a highly developed melòdic and rhythmic structure. Origin of Indian Classical Music cannot be ascribed to any particular date or time. It is believed in Indian Tradition that even before the appearance of Human Beings or even before the appearance of Living Things on Earth, there was Music. That was the Music of the spheres known as the Nada Brahma or Anāhatha Nāda. Infact there is Rhythm and Harmony at the root of the Evolution. Therefore though Music in India originated as part of religious rituals, it gradually assumed spiritual and mystical significance. The highest level of practice of Music is called Nadōpāsana (worship of God as primal sound) this music was considered to be another route to attain GOD.

Sound in Physics

In Physics sound is a vibration that propagates as an acoustic Wave. Sound is a type of Energy made by vibrations. When an object vibrates it causes movements in surrounding air molecules. They collide with the other molecules close to them causing them to vibrate as well. When we speak or Sing the air released from our lungs vibrates the vocal cord and sound is produced. Simply we can say it is a particular auditory impression- tone. It is the sensation perceived by the sense of hearing by our Ears.

Náda

Sound when rises as Music or Náda, when it is controlled. We hear a very pleasant sound which is sweet to hear. Whereas Noise is disordered, uncontrolled, unpleasant Sound. Both Music and Noise are both mixture of sound waves of different wave lengths and frequencies. Again this Náda is further divided into two forms 1) AahataNáda and AnáhataNáda. AahataNáda is produced by the conscious effort of Humans. AnáhataNáda is produced by the Music of Nature. It also includes the Náda emanating from the Mooládhára part of Human Body (kundalini Yoga). This is audible only to Yògis.

AnáhataNáda is otherwise called as “Primordial Sound”. Primordial means existing from the beginning of the Time or Life. Primordial Sounds can be considered as the Basic Vibrations of Nature such as Sound of the Wind, Sound of the Waves thrashing on the shore, Sound of the Thundering Rain, Rolling of Water in a fall, and the Entire Sound of the UNIVERSE.

Sound of the Universe

Scientists believe with every spec of energy jammed into a very tiny Point. This extremely dense point when exploded with unimaginable force , creating Matter and propelling and ejecting it outward to make the Billions of Galaxies of our Vast UNIVERSE. Astrophysicist dubbed this Titanic Explosion the Big –Bang. This Big Bang is the sound of Universe. Our Universe began with an Explosion Sound of Space itself. In Astronomy The Big –Bang Theory is a theory that suggests that the Universe was created as a result of an extremely large explosion. (Sound)

Náda of Yogi : This is one of the primordial Sound which is created through Kundalini Yoga. Primordial Sounds are Mantrás that has a tone. The vibration of the Sounds helps you center yourself and ground yourself quickly.

Náda and Music: Shiva is praised as the embodiment of Náda by many music composers.

Tyágarájar and Náda:

- 1) Nádhā thanumanisham Shankaram – Chitharanjani
- 2) Nádhā Sudhá rasam bilanu – Aarabi
- 3) Sadhá siva mayamakuNádhā òmegāra swara – Rasasudha rasa -- Anthòlika
- 4) Mooládhāra Nádhamerugide – in Swararāgasudhá -- Sankarābharanam
- 5) Nádhā lòludai brammá nandhamandave – KalyānaVasantha

2) SyāmaSāstry and Náda:

For Syāmā sāstry Sakti as the embodiment of Náda

- 1) Nádhā Roopini Jānani – Sari evvaramma –Bairavi
- 2) Samagāna Vinòdhini –Saròjadalaneethri – Sankarābharanam

3) Dikshitar and Náda:

For Dikshitar Muruga , Shiva and Shakti as embodiment of náda

- 1) Sri Nádhāthi guruguhò –Máyámálava Gowla
- 2) Sri Chithānandha Nádhā – Akilāndeshwariyai - Aarabi
- 3) Nádhā Bindhukalá roopa – Abayāmba Náyaka –Kethāragowla.

4) **ThiruMandhiram:**

For Thirumoolar Shiva as the embodiment of Náda

1) Nádhm Parathil layithidum ádhálal Nádhm ariya paramum ariyalám.

5) **Thiruppugzh:**

ArunagiriNádhm –Muruga as the embodiment of Náda

1) Nádhm Bhinduga ládhi Namò nama .

6) **AmbujamKrishna:**

Saraswathi ias the embodiment of Náda

1) Nádhm Roopini Nalvaram arulváí – Saraswathi

OHM -- PRIMORDIAL SOUND

In many Religions, culture and traditions Ohm is considered to be the Primordial Sound of the Universe and carries a divine Vibration. It is believed that the whole Universe in its more fundamental form is made up of Vibrating, pulsating, energy. Vibration produces Sound. Ohm is considered to be the Humming Sound of this cosmic energy. Ohm is said to be the primordial creative Sound from which the entire Universe has manifested. It is the original vibration the Universe. From this original vibration of the Universe all the other vibrations are able to manifest.

Omkára:

Ohm is a sacred Hindu Symbol. The Upanishads claim that Ohm is indeed God in the form of Sound. Buddhism, Sikkishm, and Jainism are also strongly associated with Ohm. The word Ohm is so much powerful that this single word can produce powerful and positive vibration. It is also known as Omkára.

Pranavá:

Ohm is also called as Pranavá and it is recited as a Mantrá. It is a Sanskrit word. According to Hindu Philosophy before existence and beyond existence, the only one reality which is represented is Ohm. According to Hindu Dharma in the Vedic tradition touts Ohm as the symbol that represents the nature of the Universe. In Hindu Cosmology Ohm is a *Bija* mantrá or sacred seed sound which created all other sounds and vibrates in our Universe. Ohm or Pranavá mantrá is the fundamental to the Vedas and it is said that everything came from Pranavá

Frequency:

Ohm when Chanted, it vibrates at the frequency of 432 HZ. The same Vibrational Frequency is found in all the things throughout Nature. So Ohm is the basic sound of the Universe. This 432HZ frequency gives a person a strong relaxation sense. A 432HZ sound ensures the brain is tuned to the Earths frequency. It is the Sruthi for Music.

Pranavá Mantrá and Music:

Pranavá or Ohmkára is praised by almost all the Composers where the deity they praise is in the form of “Ohmkára”.

Tyágarájar:

1) Sadá siva mayamaku Nádha Ohmkáraswara- in Rágasudhá Rasa- Anthòliká

2) Muthuswámi Dikshitar:

- 1) Ohmkárinī – in Annapoorne- Sama – (Anupallavi)
- 2) Ohm kárasvarupava - in Abayámba Náyak -- Ketháragowla - (Anupallavi)
- 3) Ohmkára Rupam –Ekámbara Nádham – Gamakriya – (Pallavi)
- 4) Eká nekáshari – Kanjadaláya dhákshi- Manòhari – (Charanam)
- 5) Pranavasvarupa – Vatapiganapathim- Hamshadvani- (Charanam)

3) Syámá Sásthri:

- 1) Omkári – Durusuka – Saveri – (Charanam)- 1
- 2) Omkári - Sari evvamma –Bhairavi – Charanam – 2

4) Pápanasam Sivan:

- 1) Pranavákára ganapathiye – MuládáraMúrthi – Hamsadvani – Charanam

5) Periyasámy Thooran:

- 1) Chatur vedangal Ohm Ohm ena – Gananádhane – Sárangá – Charanam

6) Mánickavásagar in Thiruvásagam:

- 1) Uyya en ullathul Onkáramái Nindra – Sivapuránam – 33rd line
Shiva himself take the form of Ohmkáram in the heart of Manickavásagar and he was able to sense the structure and sound.

7) ArunagiriNádar in Thirupugazh:

- 1) Ohm perum pranavádhi – Ettukkudi Thirupugazh

Beeja Mantrás: (Beeja means Seed)

Beeja Mantrás are also known as Vedic Seed Mantrás and are the core Mantrás or Sounds endowed with great spiritual powers. They are often the audible seed version of all deity of majority in Hinduism. Beeja mantrás form the main part of several compositions and they are like batteries of souls.

Muthuswámi Dikshitar after chanting Srividya Beeja Mantra for five years, he was blessed with a Veená by mother Ganges. In many compositions he speaks about Panchákshara Beeja Mantrá.

- 1) PanchásathpeetaRúpini –Karnátaka Devegántári - Pallavi Panchadasákshari – Anupallavi.
- 2) Sakala Manthra thanthra rupáyai Panchamaháráyai - Abayámbiká–Yadhukula Kámbòji -- Charanam
- 3) Panchákshara svarúpene – Ekámbaranádhe --Chadmangini- Anupallavi
- 4) Panchadasákshari – KanakámbariKárunyám – Kanaámbari- Charanam
- 5) Hreem kára Beejá KáraVadanám –SriKánthimadheem – Hemavathi- Anupallavi.

Syamasastri:

DivyaNámame dhyánamu vere manthra Japa thapamu lerugane – Bròvamma–Mánji.

Theváram and Panchákshará:

Thirugnána Sambandhar, Thirunávukkarasar and Sundarar Composed Panchákshara Padhigam (a set of 10 Songs)

- 1) Kádalági Kasindhu -Thirugnána Sambandhar
- 2) Sotrunai vedhiyan - Thirunávukkarasar
- 3) MatruPatrenakku - Sundarar

Manickavásagar - Thiruvásagam:

- 1) Namasiváya Vázhga – Sivapuramam – First Line
- 2) Siváyanama ena petren – Esaravu – 10th Song
- 3) Pòtri O Namasiváya - Thiru sadagam – 62nd Song.

Tyágarája and Beeja Mantrá:

Tyágarájar after chanting Rama Manthra exceeding one crore time Lord Rama appeared momentarily and gave Darshan. The whole divyanáma Kirtanai of Tyágarájar speaks about Lord Rama and His power of Nama .

Arunagirináthar and Beeja Mantrá:

Arunagirináthar speaks about Saravanabava the Shadakshara Mantra
Saravanabava nithi – Thiruvengadam thiru pugazh
Kumara gurupara muruga Saravana – Swamimalai thiru pugazh

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